

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

Available online <http://www.arseam.com>

Email us: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

A STUDY ON SERVICE MARKETING WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO FLUID CONTROL RESEARCH INSTITUTE, KANJIKODE, PALAKKAD

K.M. Najma.

Research Scholar in Commerce,
Sree Narayana Guru College, K.G.Chavadi, Coimbatore – 641 105, India

MS.D. Mahila Vasanthi Thangam

Assistant Professor, PG Department of commerce,
Sree Narayana Guru College, K.G.Chavadi Coimbatore – 641 105, India

Abstract

Today, the service sector contributes more than 50 percent to India's GDP. This is a far cry from the situation a few decades back, when India was basically an agricultural economy. This shift from manufacturing and agriculture to services is being witnessed in countries all over the world. With the increasing prominence of services in the global economy, Services Marketing has become a subject that needs to be studied separately. Service marketing is a subfield of marketing, which can be split into the two main areas of goods marketing (which includes the marketing of fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) and durables) and services marketing. Services are economic activities offered by one party to another. The present study makes an attempt to assess and analyze the service marketing in FCRI. This study identifies the importance of service in the organization. The study would help the management to know how to improve and maintain good service with their customers which is more benefit to their organization.

Key words: FMCG, FCRI, GDP, Services, Goods

INTRODUCTION

Today, the service sector contributes more than 50 percent to India's GDP. This is a far cry from the situation a few decades back, when India was basically an agricultural economy. This shift from manufacturing and agriculture to services is being witnessed in countries all over the world. With the increasing prominence of services in the global economy, Services Marketing has become a subject that needs to be studied separately. Service marketing is a subfield of marketing, which can be split into the two main areas of goods marketing (which includes the marketing of fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) and durables) and services marketing. Services are economic activities offered by one party to another. The present study makes an attempt to assess and analyze the service marketing in FCRI. This study identifies the importance of service in the organization. The study would help the management to know how to improve and maintain good service with their customers which is more benefit to their organization.

SERVICE MARKETING

Service marketing is a form of marketing which focuses on selling services. Services can be tricky to sell and the marketing approach for them is much different than the approach for products. Some companies offer both products and services and must use a mixture of styles; for example, a store which sells computers also tends to offer services such as helping people select computers and providing computer repair. Such a store must market both its products and the supporting services it offers to appeal to customers.

AN OVERVIEW OF FLUID CONTROL RESEARCH INSTITUTE

Fluid control research institute (FCRI) was established by the government of India during 1984 with the technical and financial assurance of the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) as the executing agency and M/s. instrumentation Ltd., as the implementing agency on behalf of ministry of industry.

The major objective of the institute is to provide Research and Development assistance to the flow product industry and to assist in upgrading quality and reliability of flow measurement and instrumentation. The institute acts as a National Certifying Body for flow measuring instruments. It also assists in acquiring quality conformance as per the norms of ISO 9000 series, executes sponsored Research and Development projects and undertakes training of industrial persons from India and abroad.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the needs and importance of service marketing.
- To know the special services provided by the FCRI.
- To study the problems regarding service marketing.
- To find out the effectiveness of service marketing in the firm.
- To find out which types of services are offer by the firm.
- To offer suitable suggestions to improve services in the firm.
- To find out the importance and effectiveness of training programme in FCRI.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

- This study helps to improve their quality of service.
- This study helps to detect and evaluate its own strength and weakness.
- It helps to gain knowledge about the service marketing.
- It helps to understand service mix of the firm.
- It helps to understand service efficiency of the firm.
- It helps to improve existing training in the firm.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present study makes an attempt to assess and analyze the service marketing in FCRI. This study identifies the importance of service in the organization. The study would help the management to know how to improve and maintain good service with their customers which is more benefit to their organization.

METHODOLOGY

Primary data and secondary data are used for this project. Primary data was collected through discussion with marketing dept officials of fluid control research institute.

Secondary data are collected from the booklet of FCRI and net, magazines, journals and other publication sources.

SAMPLING PROCEDURE

1. Sample unit : permanent and temporary employees in the Fluid Control Research Institute.
2. Sample size : 100 employees of FCRI
3. Sample design : simple random sampling is used for this study.
4. Sampling techniques : simple percentage method

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The decade of the 1980s saw a similar parallel between services marketing and business-to-business marketing. The former has begun to become a discipline, whereas the latter continues to be a domain. What is the difference? First of all, by the 1980s, the economy had become predominantly a services economy, and the total quality management philosophy, with its focus on customer service, had become very popular. Both the government and the industry were willing to commit money to improve product and service quality, especially in consumer mass markets. According to Sankaran M (1999) studied the measures that would help domestic players in financial services sector to improve their competitive efficiency, and thereby to reduce the transaction costs. The study found that the specific set of sources of sustainable competitive advantage relevant for Financial Service Industry are: a) product and process innovations, b) brand equity, c) positive influences of 'Communication Goods', d) corporate culture, e) experience effects, f) scale effects, and g) information technology.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table –4.1 Service Facility Provided By the Company

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	50	50%
Satisfied	30	30%
Dissatisfied	20	20%
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 50%of the respondents are highly satisfied with the service facility provided by the company, 30%of the respondents are satisfied and remaining not satisfied with the service facility of the company.

Table – 4.2 Type of Services Provided By the Company

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Tangible and intangible services	10	10%
Geographic services	0	0
Adhoc-services	10	10%
International services	10	10%
Business to Business services	60	60%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Majority of the respondents (60%) opinion is the company provides business to business services, 10% of the respondent's opinion is tangible and intangible services, 10% of the respondent's opinion is adhoc-services and rest of the opinion is international services.

Table – 4. 3 Service motto of the company

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Promoting customer satisfaction	60	60%
Building Trust	0	0
Empowering personnel	20	20%
Establishing Uniform process	20	20%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Majority of the respondents (60%) opinion is promoting customer satisfaction is the most important service motive of the company, 20% of respondents opinion is empowering the personnel and remaining (20%) of the opinion is establishing the uniform process.

Table – 4.4 Tools of Measuring Improvement of the Company

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Ranking method	50	50%
Field review method	10	10%
Grading system	30	30%
Graphic scale	10	10%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 50% of the respondents are said that the tool used to measure their company improvement is ranking method, 30% are grading system, 10% are graphic scale and rest of the respondent's opinion is field review method. So we clear that the company always rank or remark of their improvement.

Table – 4.5 Opinion about the Training Programme

Opinion	No .of respondents	Percentage
Yes	100	100%
No	-	-
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 100% of the respondents opinion is the company always conduct training and development programme. So it is clear that the company helps to find out the efficiency and improvement of their organization.

Table - 4.6 Type of training programme

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
On the job training	10	10%
Off- the job training	60	60%
Apprentice training	20	20%
Internship training	10	10%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 10% of the respondents prefer On the job training, 20% of the respondents prefer apprentice training, 10% of the respondents prefer internship training and majority of the respondents (60%) prefer Off- the job training,

Table - 4.7 Opinion Regarding Improvement of Training Programme to Staff

Opinion	No .of respondents	Percentage
Yes	100	100%
No	0	0
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 100% of the respondent said that the company can improve the training programme in an effective way.

Table - 4.8 Training Provided To Staff for the Service

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Orientation training	10	10%
Job training	40	40%
Refresher training	40	40%
Technical training	10	10%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Majority of the respondent's (40%) opinion is job training and 40% of the respondents prefer refresher training, 10% suggest that technical training and balance 10% is orientation training.

Table – 4.9 Duration of the Training programme

Opinion	No .of respondents	Percentage
Once in 3months	50	70%
Once in 6months	30	20%
Once in 9months	20	10%
Once in a year	0	0
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that majority of the respondents (70%) preferred once in 3 months period of training, 20 % preferred once in 6 months and remaining preferred once in 9 months duration of the training.

Table – 4.10 Opinion about Training Programme Provided By FCRI

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	80	80%
Satisfied	10	10%
Dissatisfied	10	10%
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 70% of respondents are highly satisfied in training, 10% of respondents are satisfied and rest of not fully satisfied.

Table – 4. 11 Instructional Aids Used By the Company

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Audio /Video visuals	50	50%
Power point presentation	30	30%
Charts& Diagrams	10	10%
Models	10	10%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 50% of the instructional aids are used by the company is audio/ video visuals, 30% of instructional aids are power point presentation, 10% of instructional aids are charts and diagrams and rest 10% of instructional aids are other models.

Table – 4. 12 Important Factor in Selecting Service

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Service	30	30%
Price	20	20%
Accurate/ accreditation	40	40%
Process	10	10%
Others	0	0
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 40% of the factors influencing & selecting their service is accreditation or accurate and another 30% of the factor is service, balance of the selecting factor is pricing and process.

Table – 4.13 Communication Media Is Used To Deliver the Service

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Telephone	20	20%
E-mail	50	50%
Fax	20	20%
Personnel	10	10%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Majority of the (50%) communication channels used by the company is E – mail, 20% is telephone, 20% is fax and rest of the 10% is personnel.

Table – 4.14 Communication Media Prefer By the Customer

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Telephone	20	20%
E-mail	50	50%
Fax	20	20%
Personnel	10	10%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

The respondents said that 50% of customers preferred e-mail, 20% of customers preferred telephone, 20% of customers preferred fax and rest of them (10%) is personnel

Table – 4.15 Satisfaction Level of Customer’s Response towards the media

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	30	30%
Satisfied	50	50%
Dissatisfied	20	20%
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Respondents said that 50% of the customers are satisfied with the media, 30% of the customers are highly satisfied and remaining not satisfied with the response towards the media.

Table – 4.16 Command / Feedback of Customers

Opinion	No .of respondents	Percentage
Yes	100	100%
No	0	0
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 100%of the respondents opinion is the company always collect command or feedback from all customers in all times.

Table – 4.17 Method Used To Collect Customer Feedback

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Observation method	10	10%
Questionnaire	10	10%
Interview	20	20%
Suggestion box	20	20%
Feedback form	40	40%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 10% of feedbacks are collected through observation method, 10% is questionnaire, 20% is interview, again 20% is suggestion box and 40% of feedbacks are collected by way of feedback form.

Table – 4.18 Kind of Service Done In FCRI

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Testing & calibration	40	40%
Quality assurance	10	10%
Training	30	30%
Research	20	20%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 40%of services are testing and calibration, 10% of services are quality assurance, 30% of services are training and remaining 20% is research.

Table – 4.19Strategies for Building Service Marketing in FCRI

Opinion	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Establishing the Brand	40	40%
Defining the service value	20	20%
Providing incentives	10	10%
Promotion	10	10%
Relationship marketing	20	20%
Total	100	100

Interpretation

Majority of the respondents (40%) opinion is establishing brand is the most important strategies of the company, 20% is defining the service value, 10% is promotion, 10% is providing incentives and remaining 20% of the opinion is relation ship marketing.

FINDINGS

The study reveals that majority of the respondents are highly satisfied with the service facility provided by the company. In FCRI, all types of services are provided, but business to business services are mostly used. Most important service motive of FCRI is promoting customer satisfaction. Ranking method is the main tool used to measure the improvement level of performance in FCRI. All respondents are willing to attend the training and development programme. The company mainly followed by the training programme is off the job training. All respondents are suggesting that the company can improve its growth through training programme. Most of the respondents gave the opinion that refresher and job training methods are mostly used for the training programme. Majority of the respondents are preferred the training period is once in 3 months. The main type of instructional aids used in FCRI is audio/ video visuals. Majority of the factors emphasis on service marketing is providing better service and accreditation facilities to its customers. Most of the respondents preferred the communication media used by the company is e – mail. Majority of the customers preferred the communication channel is e-mail and fax. All respondents are giving the opinion that the company always collects the command/ feedback from customers at all time. Most of the respondent's opinion that customers are satisfied with the communication media. The most important service done in FCRI is testing and calibration of flow meters. Majority of the respondent's opinion is company collect customer feedback through feedback form. The most important strategy followed by the company is establishing brand image and defining the service value to the customer. Service marketing is essential for the future development and growth of the organization. All the employees have a good opinion about the overall training programme conducted by the company.

SUGGESTIONS

The management should detect the deficiencies in the service facility provided by the company. The management should take appropriate steps to maintain the growth and development of the company. Appropriate measures are to be taken for the better utilization of service and training programme in the organization. The management should give better service to its customer. The organization should adopt new trends and innovations in the service marketing. The management should extend their training period from 3 months to 6 months. The company should provide safety measures to its employees. The organization should provide new techniques in the field of training programme. The management should motivate their employees for the improvement of their service. The organization should periodically collect the command/feedback from customers for the purpose of improving their service.

CONCLUSION

The study was conducted to find out the service marketing of Fluid Control Research Institute. Service marketing tool helps to find out the improvement and efficiency of the organization. It helps to know the service motive of the organization. The most important service motive of FCRI is promoting customer satisfaction. The study reveals that FCRI provide various types of services. The most important kind of service in FCRI is testing and calibration. It also provides training programmes. From the analysis of the data collected, it is clear that FCRI provide different types of training programmes and it helps staff for the improvement of their service. FCRI has conducted national and international training programmes. All employees are satisfied with the training facilities provided by the company. Marketing covers not only the marketing of goods but also the marketing of services. To conclude, FCRI is a good service providing organization.

Reference:

1. Philip Kotler: - Marketing Management: "Analysis, Planning and Control".
2. Helen Woodruffe, "Service Marketing", Macmillan
3. M.G. Parameshwaran:-"Understanding Consumers", Tata McGraw- Hill Publishing Co.Itd, New Delhi.
4. W.J. Stanton, "Fundamentals Of Marketing"
5. P.K.Akarwal."Marketing Management"Abdul assis koroth& venugopal,"human resource management".
6. Kothari, C.R, '*Research Methodology – Methods & Techniques*', (Second edition), New Delhi: WishwaPrakashan(2002).
7. RajanSaxena, '*Marketing Management*',2nd edition, New Delhi: Tata McGraw Hill(1997).
8. Bradley, N.'*Marketing Research: Tools and Techniques*'. New York, USA: Oxford University Press(2007).

Website: - www.fciiindia.com

www.wikipedia.com

www.scribd.com

www.google.com